

Rate accelerations in the hydrogenation of furyl chalcones catalyzed by anchored montmorillonite diphenyl phosphino palladium(II) chloride

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Abstract : A kinetic study of hydrogenation of furyl chalcones has been carried out with anchored montmorillonite diphenyl phosphino palladium(II) chloride as the catalyst in the temperature range of 288–306 K. Reaction kinetics indicated first order dependence on [H₂] and fractional order dependence in [catalyst] and [substrate]. A mechanism consistent with the experimental data has been proposed. The activation and thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

Keywords : Montmorillonite diphenyl phosphino palladium(II) chloride, hydrogenation, furyl chalcones, anchored catalyst.

Introduction

During the past two decades anchored catalysts received the attention of chemists all over the world owing to their increased catalytic efficiency over homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts¹⁻⁵. In recent past our group is actively involved in the hydrogenation reaction of a variety of organic compounds using montmorillonite supported palladium(II) complexes⁶⁻¹², in view of a broad spectrum of advantages such as higher dispersion of active phase, higher resistance to sintering and the ease of recycling the catalyst. Substituted acetophenones exhibit antiviral activity and especially inhibit the replication of human rhinoviruses in human embryonic lung cell¹³. The products obtained upon selective reduction of these compounds is a wide subject for the study of biological activities and would also play key role in the synthesis of several other industrially useful products¹⁴. Furyl chalcones are the substituted acetophenones containing acetophenone and furyl skeleton in the structure. Furylidine *o*-hydroxy acetophenone is the parent compound in the series of furyl chalcones (Structure A).

In the present work the selected furyl chalcones with substituents on the phenyl ring have been synthesized based on the literature reported procedure¹⁵. These compounds have been chosen for the kinetic study of hydrogenation using anchored montmorillonite diphenyl phosphino palladium(II) chloride in view of their utility for the synthesis of industrially and pharmaceutically important compounds¹⁶.

Following are some the furyl chalcones that are taken up for hydrogenation study and have been named according to the nomenclature according to the recommendations of IUPAC.

- (A) 1-(2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-3-furan-2-yl-propenone (DHPFP-1)
- (B) 3-Furan-2-yl-1-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-propenone (FHMOPP)
- (C) 3-Furan-2-yl-1-(2-hydroxymethylphenyl)-propenone (FHMPP-1)
- (D) 4-Furan-2-yl-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)propenone (FHPP)
- (E) 1-(2,5-Dihydroxyphenyl)-3-furan-2-yl-propenone (DHPFP-2)
- (F) 3-Furan-2-yl-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-propenone (FHMPP-2)
- (G) 1-(5-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-furan-2-yl-propenone (CHPFP)

Although hydrogenation reactions of simple chalcones are reported by conventional catalysts^{17,18} and also by anchored catalysts from our laboratory⁶⁻¹², hydrogenation of furyl chalcones is being reported for the first time from our laboratory.

Experimental

Materials : Anchored montmorillonite diphenylphosphino palladium(II) chloride was prepared according to the literature procedures¹⁰. Air and moisture sensitive reactions were carried out with the use of standard inert atmosphere techniques. THF was dried and deoxygenated by distilling over sodium benzophenone in nitrogen atmosphere. The substrates for hydrogenation were obtained from Aldrich. Montmorillonite clay was obtained from Fluka. Hydrogen gas employed was purified by passing over a deoxo catalyst, through molecular sieves and drying tubes before admission into the vacuum system.

Kinetic procedure : Hydrogenation reactions were carried out in a 100 ml two necked round bottomed flask. The side arm was packed with a silicone rubber septum and the other neck is attached through a three-way stop-cock, which was connected to a glass vacuum, which in

turn is equipped with a manometer, a gas burette and a gas-inlet. A known amount of the catalyst was placed in a reaction vessel and was attached to a reaction system. To this 10 ml of dry THF was added and the whole system is evacuated and flushed few times with pure hydrogen. The catalyst was activated by shaking it for 30 min in presence of hydrogen followed by inducting a known amount of substrate into it. The rate of hydrogen uptake was monitored at regular time intervals. Throughout the reaction, the reaction mixture is kept for shaking at a speed, which does not affect the rate of the reaction. The products were analyzed by IR and NMR spectroscopic methods. The uptake of hydrogen was plotted by initial rate method to obtain rate in ml/min, which is converted to mol dm⁻³ units under STP conditions.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of substrate concentration :

The rate of the reaction increased significantly with increase in concentration for the furyl chalcones. The plot of log *V* vs log [substrate] gave a linear graph with a positive slope less than unity and greater than zero and very good correlation coefficient values (Table 1). Thus the order with respect to the substrate concentration comes

Table 1. Effect of variation of [furyl chalcone] (logarithmic plots of rate (*V*) vs [furyl chalcone])

Reaction conditions : 10 ⁵ [Catalyst] : 0.40 mol dm ⁻³ ; 10 ⁻² P _{H2} : 1.063; Solvent : THF; Temperature : 288-306 K		
Entry	log <i>V</i> = <i>n</i> log [Furyl chalcone] + constant	Correlation coefficient (<i>R</i> ²)
(a) Temperature = 306 K		
DHPFP-1	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.405 (6 + log [DHPFP-1]) + 0.412	0.988
FHMOPP	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.350 (6 + log [FHMOPP]) + 0.428	0.988
FHMPP-1	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.336 (6 + log [FHMPP-1]) + 0.415	0.999
FHPP	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.344 (6 + log [FHPP]) + 0.375	0.990
DHPFP-2	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.377 (6 + log [DHPFP-2]) + 0.311	0.986
FHMPP-2	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.394 (6 + log [FHMPP-2]) + 0.253	0.987
CHFPF	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.426 (6 + log [CHFPF]) + 0.173	0.995
(b) Temperature = 300 K		
DHPFP-1	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.384 (6 + log [DHPFP-1]) + 0.420	0.998
FHMOPP	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.291 (6 + log [FHMOPP]) + 0.456	0.981
FHMPP-1	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.299 (6 + log [FHMPP-1]) + 0.425	0.988
FHPP	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.311 (6 + log [FHPP]) + 0.385	0.991
DHPFP-2	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.329 (6 + log [DHPFP-2]) + 0.335	0.981
FHMPP-2	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.341 (6 + log [FHMPP-2]) + 0.279	0.988
CHFPF	(6 + log <i>V</i>) = 0.376 (6 + log [CHFPF]) + 0.187	0.988

(c) Temperature = 288 K		
DHPFP-1	$(6 + \log V) = 0.334 (6 + \log [\text{DHPFP-1}]) + 0.458$	0.993
FHMOPP	$(6 + \log V) = 0.254 (6 + \log [\text{FHMOPP}]) + 0.479$	0.995
FHMPP-1	$(6 + \log V) = 0.269 (6 + \log [\text{FHMPP-1}]) + 0.418$	0.987
FHPP	$(6 + \log V) = 0.277 (6 + \log [\text{FHPP}]) + 0.371$	0.987
DHPFP-2	$(6 + \log V) = 0.279 (6 + \log [\text{DHPFP-2}]) + 0.334$	0.992
FHMPP-2	$(6 + \log V) = 0.298 (6 + \log [\text{FHMPP-2}]) + 0.261$	0.983
CHPFP	$(6 + \log V) = 0.326 (6 + \log [\text{CHPFP}]) + 0.168$	0.986

out to be fractional. Further the plot of V vs [substrate] indicated a curve with linearity in low concentration region followed by a maximum a rate at higher concentrations (Fig. 1A). These observations indicate the formation of precursor between furyl chalcones with catalyst prior to rate limiting step.

Effect of variation of catalyst concentration :

Hydrogenation of furyl chalcones did not proceed even under drastic conditions in the absence of catalyst. However, the reaction proceeds smoothly in the presence of the catalyst. The rate of hydrogenation showed an increasing trend when the experiments were carried out at different temperatures ranging from 288 to 306 K with increase in the catalyst concentration. The plots of $\log V$ vs $\log [C]$ gave a straight line with a positive slope less than unity indicating order with respect to [catalyst] is fractional.

Representative results are presented in the form of straight line equations (Table 2; Fig. 1B).

Effect of variation of partial pressures of hydrogen :

Plots of $\log V$ vs $\log P_{\text{H}_2}$ gave a straight line with a positive slope approximately equivalent to unity indicating the first order with respect to partial pressure of hydrogen, when the partial pressure of hydrogen was varied in the range 101.5 KN m^{-2} to 109.5 KN m^{-2} keeping all other reactants and reaction conditions constant, similar observations were made in case of all other substrates (Table 3).

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by mole-ratio method. The stoichiometry of the reactions was found to be [substrate] : P_{H_2} as 1 : 3 for all the substrates. Proton NMR

Fig. 1(A). Plot of [DHPFP-1] vs rate, 10^5 [Catalyst] : 0.40 mol dm^{-3} ; $10^{-2} P_{\text{H}_2}$: 1.063; solvent : THF; temperature : 288–306 K.

Fig. 1(B). Plot of $1/[\text{DHPFP-1}]$ vs $1/K$.

Table 2. Effect of variation of [catalyst] (logarithmic plots of rate (V) vs [catalyst])

Reaction conditions : 10^5 [Substrate] : 0.75 mol dm^{-3} ; $10^{-2} P_{H_2}$: 1.063 kNm^{-2} ; Temperature : 288–306 K. Rate $\times 10^6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$; Solvent : THF

Entry	$\log V = n \log [\text{Catalyst}] + \text{constant}$	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
(a) Temperature = 306 K		
DHPFP-1	$(7 + \log V) = 0.700 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.088$	0.997
FHMOPP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.718 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.140$	0.996
FHMPP-1	$(7 + \log V) = 0.735 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.201$	0.999
FHPP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.745 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.247$	0.999
DHPFP-2	$(7 + \log V) = 0.753 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.271$	0.999
FHMPP-2	$(7 + \log V) = 0.773 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.342$	0.998
CHPFP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.794 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.416$	0.999
(b) Temperature = 300 K		
DHPFP-1	$(7 + \log V) = 0.679 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.078$	0.997
FHMOPP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.672 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.117$	0.993
FHMPP-1	$(7 + \log V) = 0.702 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.176$	0.991
FHPP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.680 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.183$	0.997
DHPFP-2	$(7 + \log V) = 0.693 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.233$	0.998
FHMPP-2	$(7 + \log V) = 0.723 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.311$	0.999
CHPFP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.738 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.384$	0.999
(c) Temperature = 288 K		
DHPFP-1	$(7 + \log V) = 0.656 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.078$	0.998
FHMOPP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.654 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.106$	0.999
FHMPP-1	$(7 + \log V) = 0.674 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.169$	0.999
FHPP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.645 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.170$	0.999
DHPFP-2	$(7 + \log V) = 0.664 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.229$	0.999
FHMPP-2	$(7 + \log V) = 0.689 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.313$	0.999
CHPFP	$(7 + \log V) = 0.711 (6 + \log [\text{Catalyst}]) - 0.401$	0.998

spectroscopic data of certain furyl chalcones and corresponding products are presented in the Table 4.

Effect of temperature : With increase in temperature the rates of hydrogenation increased. The reactions were carried out in the temperature range 288–306 K. The rates of hydrogenation of chalcones have been found to be relatively less when compared to cinnamic acid and other aliphatic olefins studied in other sections of this work.

Although the out come appears to be governed largely by steric factors, the hydrogenation is also sensitive to the nature of the catalyst, solvent and pressure. In addition to this the interlayer distance of the clay also plays a dominant role in the hydrogenation reaction. Smaller reactant and product molecules diffuse in and out of the swellable interlayer of montmorillonite easily, which enables the new reactant molecules ready for the hydrogenation. The small molecules undergo complexation easily in the interlayer of montmorillonite. The size of the furyl chalcones fall in the range $\sim 8.48\text{--}12.20 \text{ \AA}$ whereas the interlayer distance of the catalyst is $\sim 15 \text{ \AA}$. The furyl chalcone being a bulkier molecule rate of diffusion in and out of the interlayers of the catalyst decreases and hence this causes lower rate of hydrogenation. Thus the slow

Table 3. Effect of variation of partial pressure of hydrogen (logarithmic plots of rate (V) vs [P_{H₂}])

Reaction conditions : 10⁵ [Substrate] : 0.75 mol dm⁻³; 10⁵ [Catalyst] : 0.40 mol dm⁻³; Solvent : THF; Temperature : 288–306 K

Entry	log V = n log [P _{H₂}] + constant	Correlation coefficient (R ²)
(a) Temperature = 306 K		
DHPFP-1	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.300	0.998
FHMOPP	(6 + log V) = 1.03 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.318	0.987
FHMPP-1	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.377	0.997
FHPP	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.386	0.997
DHPFP-2	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.422	0.997
FHMPP-2	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.470	0.997
CHPFP	(6 + log V) = 1.06 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.530	0.997
(b) Temperature = 300 K		
DHPFP-1	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.310	0.997
FHMOPP	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.340	0.997
FHMPP-1	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.381	0.997
FHPP	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.422	0.997
DHPFP-2	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.451	0.998
FHMPP-2	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.515	0.997
CHPFP	(6 + log V) = 1.06 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.582	0.997
(b) Temperature = 288 K		
DHPFP-1	(6 + log V) = 1.06 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.367	0.998
FHMOPP	(6 + log V) = 1.03 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.340	0.997
FHMPP-1	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.430	0.997
FHPP	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.458	0.996
DHPFP-2	(6 + log V) = 1.04 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.493	0.996
FHMPP-2	(6 + log V) = 1.05 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.570	0.997
CHPFP	(6 + log V) = 1.08 (6 + log [P _{H₂}]) - 1.300	0.996

rates of the hydrogenation could be attributed mainly to the bulkier substituents present on the olefinic bond. The rate of hydrogenation for the substituted furyl chalcones was found to be decreasing in the order :

Even though the olefinic part of the compound is expected to get reduced, the furan ring also underwent reduction in the above compounds giving the following products.

where : A' – 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)propanone – TDHPP-1

B' – 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)propanone – THMOPP

C' – 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(2-hydroxy-4-methylphenyl)propanone – THMPP-1

D' – 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)propanone – THPP

E' – 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(2,5-dihydroxyphenyl)propanone – TDHPP-2

Table 4. ¹H NMR data of the substrates and products

Substrate	NMR (δ)	Product	NMR (δ)
A	6.41 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.82 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.95–8.00 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 12.5 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	A'	1.84 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 2.9 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.7 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 3.80 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 6.43 (2H, m, C ₅ -H and C ₃ -H), 7.81 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 12.2 (bs, phenolic -OH)
B	3.79 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 6.43 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.85 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.9–8.0 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 12.9 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	B'	1.85 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 2.9 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.69 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 3.80 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 3.81 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 6.45 (2H, m, C ₅ -H and C ₃ -H), 7.79 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 12.2 (bs, phenolic -OH)
C	2.5 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.4 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.81 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.91–7.9 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 13.0 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	C'	1.86 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 2.29 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.7 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 2.5 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.80 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 6.45 (2H, m, C ₅ -H and C ₃ -H), 7.80 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 12.2 (bs, phenolic -OH)
D	6.4 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.8 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.95–7.9 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 12.8 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	D'	1.86 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 3.0 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.7 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 3.85 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 6.5 (2H, m, C ₅ -H and C ₃ -H), 7.40 (1H, m, C ₄ -H), 7.8 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 12.3 (bs, phenolic -OH)
E	6.38 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.79 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.80–7.9 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 12.5 (bs, phenolic -OH proton), 12.7 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	E'	1.85 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 2.8 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.74 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 3.80 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 7.3 (1H, m, C ₄ -H and C ₃ -H), 6.45 (1H, m, C ₃ -H), 7.80 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 12.1 (bs, phenolic -OH), 12.2 (bs, phenolic -OH)
F	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.4 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.77 (1H, olefinic), 6.80–7.9 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 12.8 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	F'	1.85 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 2.5 (3H, s, CH ₃ -C ₅), 2.79 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.74 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 3.79 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 7.35 (1H, m, C ₄ -H), 7.8 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 6.50 (1H, m, C ₃ -H), 12.3 (bs, phenolic -OH)
G	6.4 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.77 (1H, d, olefinic), 6.80–7.9 (6H, m, phenyl and furyl protons), 12.8 (bs, phenolic -OH proton)	G'	1.85 (6H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂ -3 of furan), 2.79 (2H, m, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2 \end{array}$), 3.74 (1H, m, C ₂ -H of furan), 3.79 (2H, m, C ₅ -OCH ₂), 7.35 (1H, m, C ₄ -H), 7.8 (1H, m, C ₆ -H), 6.50 (1H, m, C ₃ -H), 12.3 (bs, phenolic -OH)

F' - 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-propanone - THMPP-2

G' - 3-tetrahydrofuran-1-(5-chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-propanone - TCHPP

Mechanism of hydrogenation :

On the basis of foregoing kinetic results i.e. first order with respect to partial pressure of hydrogen and fractional order with respect to substrate concentration and

catalyst concentration a plausible mechanism was proposed.

where C is the catalyst employed in the reaction, C₁ is the intermediate hydrido complex formed between Pd^{II} and hydrogen, C₂ is the π-complex formed in the second equilibrium step due to the interaction of C₁ with olefinic double bond of the substrate (S) and 'P₁' is the first stage-hydrogenated product. However, a detailed mechanism is shown in Scheme 1. The product thus formed in the slow step of first stage (P₁) further reduced to give the end product through a sequence of fast steps shown in second and third stages of Scheme 1. Rate law for the sequence of steps given in Scheme 1 could be given as,

$$V = \frac{dP}{dt} = k [C_2]$$

Substitution for [C₂] in the above equation affords the following rate equation

$$V = \frac{kK_1K_2 [C][H_2][S]}{1 + K_1 [C] + K_2 [S] + K_1K_2 [C][S]}$$

Rearranging the equation,

$$k' = \frac{V}{[H_2]} = \frac{kK_1K_2 [C][S]}{1 + K_1 [C] + K_2 [S] + K_1K_2 [C][S]}$$

Taking reciprocals of the above equation

$$1/k' = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2 [C][S]} + \frac{1}{kK_2 [S]} + \frac{1}{kK_1 [C]} + \frac{1}{k}$$

Scheme 1. Mechanism for the hydrogenation of furyl chalcones.

According to the above equation, at constant catalyst concentration, least square plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[S]$ gave a straight line with a positive slope and intercept. This observation is in accordance with the proposed mechanism.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2 [C]} + \frac{1}{kK_2}$$

and

$$\text{Intercept} = \frac{1}{kK_1 [C]} + \frac{1}{k}$$

The ratio of intercept to slope gave K_2 , which was determined at different temperature from which ΔH has been calculated. The free energy values related to K_2 were obtained from Vant Hoff's reaction isotherm i.e.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_2$$

and ΔS was calculated from the equation

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$$

The values obtained for ΔH , ΔG and ΔS were all negative indicating the feasible formation of the complex C_2 .

Similarly the least square plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[C]$ at constant substrate concentration gave straight line with a positive slope and intercept. From the ratio of intercept and slope K_1 was evaluated. The rate constant of the slow step (k) was evaluated at different temperatures and also from the intercept of plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[S]$. The corresponding activation parameters have been calculated and presented (Tables 5 and 6). The corresponding thermodynamic parameters have been calculated and presented

Table 5. Reciprocal plots of rate vs [furyl chalcone] $\{(1/k') \text{ vs } (1/[\text{furyl chalcone}])\}$

Reaction conditions : 10^5 [Catalyst] : 0.40 mol dm⁻³; 10^{-2} P_H₂ : 1.063; Solvent : THF; Temperature : 288–306 K

($y = 1/k'$, $x = \text{Furyl chalcone}$)

Entry	$(1/k') = (m[\text{Furyl chalcone}]) + c$ $Y = mx + c$	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
(a) Temperature = 306 K		
DHPFP-1	$(1/k') = (0.782 \times 10^3/[\text{DHPFP-1}]) + 0.781 \times 10^5$	0.999
FHMOPP	$(1/k') = (0.675 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMOPP}]) + 0.995 \times 10^5$	0.993
FHMPP-1	$(1/k') = (0.662 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMPP-1}]) + 1.11 \times 10^5$	0.973
FHPP	$(1/k') = (0.757 \times 10^3/[\text{FHPP}]) + 1.16 \times 10^5$	0.991
DHPFP-2	$(1/k') = (0.898 \times 10^3/[\text{DHPFP-2}]) + 1.17 \times 10^5$	0.996
FHMPP-2	$(1/k') = (1.03 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMPP-2}]) + 1.30 \times 10^5$	0.997
CHPFP	$(1/k') = (1.21 \times 10^3/[\text{CHPFP}]) + 1.30 \times 10^5$	0.993
(b) Temperature = 300 K		
DHPFP-1	$(1/k') = (0.734 \times 10^3/[\text{DHPFP-1}]) + 0.868 \times 10^5$	0.997
FHMOPP	$(1/k') = (0.617 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMOPP}]) + 1.19 \times 10^5$	0.997
FHMPP-1	$(1/k') = (0.661 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMPP-1}]) + 1.24 \times 10^5$	0.994
FHPP	$(1/k') = (0.724 \times 10^3/[\text{FHPP}]) + 1.30 \times 10^5$	0.991
DHPFP-2	$(1/k') = (0.841 \times 10^3/[\text{DHPFP-2}]) + 1.34 \times 10^5$	0.998
FHMPP-2	$(1/k') = (0.946 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMPP-2}]) + 1.46 \times 10^5$	0.994
CHPFP	$(1/k') = (1.19 \times 10^3/[\text{CHPFP}]) + 1.54 \times 10^5$	0.996
(c) Temperature = 288 K		
DHPFP-1	$(1/k') = (0.681 \times 10^3/[\text{DHPFP-1}]) + 0.985 \times 10^5$	0.990
FHMOPP	$(1/k') = (0.585 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMOPP}]) + 1.304 \times 10^5$	0.995
FHMPP-1	$(1/k') = (0.648 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMPP-1}]) + 1.43 \times 10^5$	0.993
FHPP	$(1/k') = (0.732 \times 10^3/[\text{FHPP}]) + 1.54 \times 10^5$	0.994
DHPFP-2	$(1/k') = (0.789 \times 10^3/[\text{DHPFP-2}]) + 1.66 \times 10^5$	0.991
FHMPP-2	$(1/k') = (0.968 \times 10^3/[\text{FHMPP-2}]) + 1.81 \times 10^5$	0.997
CHPFP	$(1/k') = (1.12 \times 10^3/[\text{CHPFP}]) + 1.99 \times 10^5$	0.996

Table 6. Reciprocal plots of rate vs [catalyst] $\{(1/k') \text{ vs } (1/[\text{catalyst}])\}$

Reaction conditions : 10^5 [Substrate] : 0.75 mol dm^{-3} ; 10^{-2} P^{H}_2 : 1.063 kNm^{-2} ; Temperature : 288–306 K; Rate $\times 10^6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$;
Solvent : THF ($y = 1/k' \text{ x = Catalyst}$)

Entry	$(1/k') = (m/[\text{Catalyst}]) + c$ $Y = mx + c$	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
(a) Temperature = 306 K		
DHPFP-1	$(1/k') = (0.226 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.403 \times 10^5$	0.999
FHMOPP	$(1/k') = (0.245 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.419 \times 10^5$	0.995
FHMPP-1	$(1/k') = (0.272 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.437 \times 10^5$	0.996
FHPP	$(1/k') = (0.298 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.449 \times 10^5$	0.997
DHPFP-2	$(1/k') = (0.312 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.447 \times 10^5$	0.996
FHMPP-2	$(1/k') = (0.353 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.461 \times 10^5$	0.997
CHPFP	$(1/k') = (0.399 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.478 \times 10^5$	0.996
(b) Temperature = 300 K		
DHPFP-1	$(1/k') = (0.227 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.464 \times 10^5$	0.997
FHMOPP	$(1/k') = (0.248 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.540 \times 10^5$	0.995
FHMPP-1	$(1/k') = (0.269 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.516 \times 10^5$	0.995
FHPP	$(1/k') = (0.285 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.596 \times 10^5$	0.996
DHPFP-2	$(1/k') = (0.316 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.606 \times 10^5$	0.997
FHMPP-2	$(1/k') = (0.353 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.619 \times 10^5$	0.995
CHPFP	$(1/k') = (0.409 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.661 \times 10^5$	0.996
(c) Temperature = 288 K		
DHPFP-1	$(1/k') = (0.236 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.527 \times 10^5$	0.998
FHMOPP	$(1/k') = (0.246 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.593 \times 10^5$	0.992
FHMPP-1	$(1/k') = (0.274 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.618 \times 10^5$	0.991
FHPP	$(1/k') = (0.287 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.731 \times 10^5$	0.990
DHPFP-2	$(1/k') = (0.318 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.752 \times 10^5$	0.999
FHMPP-2	$(1/k') = (0.374 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.781 \times 10^5$	0.991
CHPFP	$(1/k') = (0.439 \times 10^3/[\text{Catalyst}]) + 0.845 \times 10^5$	0.990

(Table 7). The negative values obtained for ΔG , ΔH and ΔS indicate the formation of C_1 .

In order to know the effect of structure on the reacti-

vity (Figs. 2.1–2.9) upon substitution on furyl chalcones studies had been carried out and the data are cast into Hammett's equation. The plot of $\log k/k_0$ vs σ was a

Table 7. Activation parameters and thermodynamic parameters involving K_1 and K_2

Sl. no.	Olefins	Activation parameters			Thermodynamic parameters involving K_1 and K_2					
		$10^{-5} \times k_{306} \text{ s}^{-1}$	ΔH (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	K_1	$-\Delta H_1$ (kJ mol^{-1})	$-\Delta S_1$ ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	K_2	$-\Delta H_2$ (kJ mol^{-1})	$-\Delta S_2$ ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)
1.	A	4.72	20.7	126	177	17.5	14.1	204	15.8	12.7
2.	B	4.51	31.7	90.6	171	30.9	58.2	218	16.6	14.3
3.	C	3.73	26.9	107	160	22.6	31.6	191	22.4	30.7
4.	D	3.66	49.6	33.5	150	41.6	94.3	208	13.4	14.4
5.	E	3.56	40.9	62.5	143	37.1	79.9	191	19.7	27.4
6.	F	3.33	43.5	54.4	130	37.3	87.4	175	26.2	42.3
7.	G	3.22	47.3	41.9	119	38.3	85.2	161	20.6	23.7

2.1 : Plot of $\log k/k_0$ (y-axis) vs σ (x-axis).

2.2 : Plot of $\log K_1/K^*_1$ (y-axis) vs σ (x-axis).

2.3 : Plot of $\log K_2/K^*_2$ (y-axis) vs σ (x-axis).

2.4 : Plot of $\log k_{(306\text{ K})}$ (y-axis) vs $\log k_{(300\text{ K})}$ (x-axis).

2.5 : Plot of $\log K_1(306\text{ K})$ (y-axis) vs $\log K_1(300\text{ K})$ (x-axis).

2.6 : Plot of $\log K_2(306\text{ K})$ (y-axis) vs $\log K_2(300\text{ K})$ (x-axis).

2.7 : Plot of $-\Delta S^*$ (y-axis) vs $-\Delta H^\ddagger$ (x-axis).

2.8 : Plot of $-\Delta S_1$ (y-axis) vs $-\Delta H_1$ (x-axis).

2.9 : Plot of $-\Delta S_2$ (y-axis) vs $-\Delta H_2$ (x-axis).

Fig. 2. Structure reactivity graphs.

straight line with a negative slope of value -0.220 and a correlation coefficient equal to 0.870 . Slope of the Hammett's plot represents reaction constant $[\rho]$. Though the negative values of ρ indicate that the electron donating substituents increase the rate of the reaction, these values do not appear to have much significance for the hydrogenation of furyl chalcones. This may be probably due to the furan ring hydrogenation in addition to the hydrogenation of olefinic bond. This point could be further strengthened from the information obtained from similar type of Hammett's plots for formation constants C_1 and C_2 , which indicated positive slopes (0.582 and 0.304) with poor correlation coefficient 0.857 and 0.665 respectively. The smaller magnitudes of observed ρ values (with poor correlation coefficients) may also indicate that the reaction rates are not very much sensitive to the substituents on the phenyl ring of substrate as the phenyl ring is far away from the reaction site.

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